

1 **MICA and MICB engagement demonstrates specific functional requirements for MHC**
2 **receptor-mediated processes during ES cell commitment in humans.**

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7 We measured total transcription in the inner cell mass (ICM) and the trophectoderm (TE) of the human
8 embryo to understand the mechanisms underlying TE commitment. We describe here discovery of
9 specific functional requirements for MHC receptor-mediated processes as a lineage commitment factor or
10 lineage commitment cooperating factor in embryonic stem cells of the human embryo indicated by
11 utilization of MICA and MICB during exit from pluripotency.

12 Citations

13 1. Ferrari de Andrade, L., Tay, R.E., Pan, D., Luoma, A.M., Ito, Y., Badrinath, S., Tsoucas, D., Franz,
14 B., May Jr, K.F., Harvey, C.J. and Kobold, S., 2018. Antibody-mediated inhibition of MICA and MICB
15 shedding promotes NK cell-driven tumor immunity. *Science*, 359(6383), pp.1537-1542.